

REPOPULATING AND REWILDING A HISTORICAL AGRICULTURAL LANDSCAPE: 2030-2100 TRANSITION

Supplementary Material

1. Model Parameters

The model is based on Lotka-Volterra equations, in which four species interact. In the parameter matrix $\mathbf{r}$ is the growth rate, $\mathbf{p}$ is the initial population, $\mathbf{K}$ is the carrying capacity and $\mathbf{A}$ is the amplitude of a sin function. Also, the **alpha** matrix elements are the influence in each yearly iteration of one member of a column species onto a member of a row column species. The four lists in brackets relate to acorn, boar, wolf and human, respectively.

The code can be found at <https://github.com/EmmanuelCastillo87/Sus-Scrofa/tree/main>

2. Sensitivity analysis

In the first run, the alpha matrix was per the reference simulation and each successive model (1-6 below) was a two-fold increase, compared to the reference, *ceteris paribus*:

1. All species r ,
2. All species p ,
3. human K ,
4. acorn r and p ,
5. boar r and p ,
6. wolf r and p ,

In the second run the human growth rate and its carrying capacity was restricted:

7. human r lowered 10 times and human $K=100$,
8. human r lowered 10 times and human $K=100$ in a 200-year simulation
9. Net human pressure (alpha) on acorn became positive and grew 7.5 times in absolute value ($-0.1 \rightarrow 0.75$)

p (the initial 2030 population of each species) in the Python code was denoted P_0 in the published article, for clarity.

In the third run, the pressure of humans on boar was relieved ($-0.9 \rightarrow -0.1$) and human positive pressure on wolf was annulled ($0.00039 \rightarrow 0$). Other modifications were, *ceteris paribus*:

10. All species rates doubled compared to reference (similar to Run 1)
11. All species p doubled, except for humans
12. K doubled in humans.

In the fourth run, r , p and K were doubled, one species at a time (models 13-16).

FIRST RUN (same alphas as reference)

Alpha= [[0, -0.1, 0, -0.1], [0, 0, -1, -0.9], [0, 0, 0, 0.00039], [0, 0, 0, 0]]

1. Rates (r) are doubled: final boar population was two times higher than reference, because the acorn grew almost twice as much. **Wolf oscillated around their carrying capacity.**

Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.030, 'p': 31300, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},

 {'name': 'boar', 'r': 1.0, 'p': 300, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},

 {'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.8, 'p': 4, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

 {'name': 'human', 'r': 0.212, 'p': 1900, 'K': 2500, 'A': 0.05}]

2. p was doubled, except humans: boar were as controlled as reference. The favorable pressure of acorn and boar balanced out the (nine fold) negative pressure of human on boar.

Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015, 'p': 62600, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5, 'p': 600, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4, 'p': 8, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

{'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106, 'p': 1900, 'K': 2500, 'A': 0.05}]

3. K was doubled in humans: boar extinction in <3 decades while **wolf overshoot their K**, but achieve stationarity.

Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015, 'p': 31300, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5, 'p': 300, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4, 'p': 4, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

{'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106, 'p': 1900, 'K': 5000, 'A': 0.05}]

4. r and p was doubled for acorn: boar were as controlled as reference. The favorable pressure of acorn and boar balanced out the (nine fold) negative pressure of human on boar.

Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.030, 'p': 62600, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},

 {'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5, 'p': 300, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},

 {'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4, 'p': 4, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

 {'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106, 'p': 1900, 'K': 2500, 'A': 0.05}]

5. r and p was doubled for boar: boar population double and acorn were reduced by one fifth.

```
Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015, 'p': 31300, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},  
          {'name': 'boar', 'r': 1, 'p': 600, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},  
          {'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4, 'p': 4, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},  
          {'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106, 'p': 1900, 'K': 2500, 'A': 0.05}]
```


6. r and p doubled for wolf: all dynamics as per reference, with Wolf overshoot their carrying capacity. Low impact on boar by duplicate wolf growth rate and p . **Pendular Wolf growth and degrowth around stationarity.**

Species=[{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015, 'p': 31300, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5, 'p': 300, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.8, 'p': 8, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

{'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106, 'p': 1900, 'K': 2500, 'A': 0.05}]

SECOND RUN (same alphas as reference)

Alpha= [[0, -0.1, 0, -0.1], [0, 0, -1, -0.9], [0, 0, 0, 0.00039], [0, 0, 0, 0]]

7. Human rate lowered 10 times, and K=100: Wolf only species as reference. Acorn slight decrease, boar ocilates below K, human do not reach one hundred (153) ->

Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015, 'p': 31300, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},

 {'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5, 'p': 300, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},

 {'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4, 'p': 4, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

 {'name': 'human', 'r': 0.012, 'p': 1900, 'K': 100, 'A': 0.05}]

8. Same as model 7, 200 years: **Human reach one hundred after 125 years**, boar at K, and acorn grow as human pressure on acorn decreases.

9. Human pressure on acorn became positive (-0.1 -> 0.75): Acorn K reached within simulation period (70 years) almost exactly.

Alpha= [[0, -0.1, 0, **0.75**], [0, 0, -1, -0.9], [0, 0, 0, 0.00039], [0, 0, 0, 0]]

Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015, 'p': 31300, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},

 {'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5, 'p': 300, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},

 {'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4, 'p': 4, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

 {'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106, 'p': 1900, 'K': 2500, 'A': 0.05}]

THIRDRH RUN (different alpha from reference, reference is Figs. 4 and 5 in the article):

Alpha= [[0, -0.1, 0, -0.1], [0, 0, -1, -0.1], [0, 0, 0, 0], [0, 0, 0, 0]]

10. r is doubled: boar couldn't be controlled, **Wolf oscillates around K**

Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.030, 'p': 31300, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},

 {'name': 'boar', 'r': 1.0, 'p': 300, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},

 {'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.8, 'p': 4, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

 {'name': 'human', 'r': 0.212, 'p': 1900, 'K': 2500, 'A': 0.05}]

11. p was doubled, except humans: boars could not eat enough acorn early on. The acorn may be collected for swine production, inhibiting the boar's growth. But there is a limit to the harvest.

```
Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015, 'p': 62600, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},
          {'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5, 'p': 600, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},
          {'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4, 'p': 8, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},
          {'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106, 'p': 1900, 'K': 2500, 'A': 0.05}]
```


12. K was doubled in humans: boar was controlled but at high level and the acorn increased only one fourth of the reference model.

Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015, 'p': 31300, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5, 'p': 300, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4, 'p': 4, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

{'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106, 'p': 1900, 'K': 5000, 'A': 0.05}]

FOURTH RUN (same alphas as reference)

Alpha matrix per published reference model

13. Acorn r,p, K doubled: acorn did not reach K, boar inhibited as reference and boar not favored by acorn growth

Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015*2, 'p': 31300*2, 'K': 122000*2, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5, 'p': 300, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4, 'p': 4, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

{'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106, 'p': 1900, 'K': 2500, 'A': 0.05}]

14. Boar r, p, K doubled: acorn very inhibited and boar grew five-fold but below boar K (due to human pressure)

Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015, 'p': 31300, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5*2, 'p': 300*2, 'K': 6000*2, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4, 'p': 4, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

{'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106, 'p': 1900, 'K': 2500, 'A': 0.05}]

15. Wolf r,p, K doubled: **Wolf oscillated around K**

```
Species=[{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015, 'p': 31300, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},  
{'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5, 'p': 300, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},  
{'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4*2, 'p': 4*2, 'K': 12*2, 'A': 0.15},  
{'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106, 'p': 1900, 'K': 2500, 'A': 0.05}]
```


16. Human r, p, K doubled: **Boar goes extinct in 20 years, Wolf overshoots K** as human favorable pressure on Wolf remains the same but more humans are present.

Species= [{'name': 'acorn', 'r': 0.015, 'p': 31300, 'K': 122000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'boar', 'r': 0.5, 'p': 300, 'K': 6000, 'A': 0.1},

{'name': 'wolf', 'r': 0.4, 'p': 4, 'K': 12, 'A': 0.15},

{'name': 'human', 'r': 0.106*2, 'p': 1900*2, 'K': 2500*2, 'A': 0.05}]

3. Runs summary

Model	Variations on species parameters	Variations on alpha matrix	Max population				Mean stable population				Year stabilization population			
			A	B	W	H	A	B	W	H	A	B	W	H
1	2*r	-	75000	4000	11	2530	-	2700	12	2480	-	22	15	23
2	2*p(-h)	-	78000	1700	16	2510	-	1500	11	2470	-	40	11	55
3	2*K(h)	=	43000	800	11	5015	-	0	14	5000	-	30	38	57
4	2*r(a), 2*p(a)	-	97000	1500	11	2520	-	1540	10	2475	-	21	13	51
5	2*r(b), 2*p(b)	-	42000	4200	14	2510	-	3850	11	2495	-	26	12	45
6	2*r(w), 2*p(w)	-	51000	1500	11	2505	-	1475	12	2495	-	20	21	47
7	1/10*r(h), k(h)=100	-	48000	6000	11	1900	-	5500	11	250	-	50	12	67
8*	1/10*r(h), k(h)=100	-	65000	6100	11	1900	-	5830	10	95	-	100	13	125
9	-	(h,a,0.75)	121000	1600	11	2520	-	1580	11	2490	-	13	20	49
10	2*r	(h,b,-0.1); (h,f,0)	68000	5300	13	2515	-	5800	11	2490	-	11	14	20
11	2*p(-h)	(h,b,-0.1); (h,f,0)	64000	5750	11	2510	6400	5500	10	2495	12	22	13	53
12	2*K(h)	(h,b,-0.1); (h,f,0)	40000	5400	14	5010	-	5000	10	5000	-	20	10	55
13	2*r(a), 2*p(a), 2*K(a)	-	168000	1650	11	2510	-	1570	11	2480	-	20	10	44
14	2*r(b), 2*p(b), 2*K(b)	-	32000	11000	11	2515	31500	10000	10	2460	5	16	12	40
15	2*r(w), 2*p(w), 2*K(w)	-	51000	1670	26	2510	-	1650	24	2490	-	21	18	45
16	2*r(h), 2*p(h), 2*K(h)	-	50000	300	16	5050	-	0	14	4900	-	12	12	18

*Run 2030 through 2230.

4. Sensitive analysis of the model:

Wild boar controlled: 1, 2, 4, 6, 9, 13, 15 (scenarios)

Wild boar extinguished: 3, 16 (scenarios)

Wild boar reached K: 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 14 (scenarios)

Humans always reach K.

Wolf always oscillates around K. On scenario 15 doubles K. On scenarios 2, 5, 10, 12 and 16 oscillates amplitude is around 3 (25%).

Acorn usually grow linear. Scenario 9 and 13 emulates reforestation. On scenarios, 11 and 14 there are not growth nor decline. On scenarios 1, 2, 4, 10 and 11 the slope is steeper (where there is no changes on humans and boar parameters).